

An event stream architecture for the distributed inference execution of predictive monitoring models

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Abstract— Predictive monitoring on distributed critical infrastructures (DCI) is the ability to anticipate events that will likely occur in the DCI before they actually appear, improving the response time to avoid the rise of critical incidents. Distributed into a region or country, DCIs such as smart grids or microgrids rely on IoT, edge-fog continuum computing and the growing capabilities of distributed application architectures to collect, transport, and process data generated by the infrastructure. We present a model-agnostic distributed architecture for the inference execution of machine learning window-based prediction models of predictive monitoring applications to be used in this context. This architecture transports the events generated by the DCI using event streams to be processed by a hierarchy of nodes holding predictive models. It also handles the offloading of inferences from resource-scarce devices at lower levels to the resourceful upper nodes. Therefore, the timing requirements for setting predictions before they occur are met.

Index Terms— distributed critical infrastructures, predictive monitoring, machine learning models inference on the edge, hierarchical distributed architecture, streams based architecture

I. DISTRIBUTED CRITICAL INFRASTRUCTURES

A Critical Infrastructure is defined as one whose assets, systems, and networks are considered vital to society because their incapacitation or destruction would have a debilitating effect on security, national economic security, national public health or safety, or any combination thereof [1]. Within them, microgrids, in the context of Smart Grids (SG), are a good example of distributed critical infrastructure (DCI), as their physical assets are geographically distributed, requiring a communication and control network to maintain its integrity and perform its functions.

Microgrids (MG) are groups of interconnected loads and distributed energy resources with electrical boundaries that act as single controllable entities with respect to the grid. They build a hierarchical infrastructure to manage power distribution [2, 3]. They contain a large number of sensors such as smart meters (able to convert numeric measurements such as voltage or current into events whenever thresholds are surpassed), gateways, and microgrid controllers acting as local nodes, aggregation zonal nodes for substations, control centers running the Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition systems (SCADA), and distribution management systems. As strategic assets, they operate mostly on a private infrastructure (networks, computing resources, sensors, and actuators).

Predictive monitoring [4] is the ability to predict events that will occur in the MG based on the observation of its current state and the application of Machine Learning (ML) predictive methods. [5,6] review their applications in the field of Smart

Grids. This capability helps to forecast the near future, check if the expected situation of the MG puts it at risk, and apply corrective actions immediately before a dangerous situation occurs. High-quality ML models help accurately identify these risky situations.

ML predictive models are generated by training using datasets with historical system event data records, and this training process is performed offline, as it requires a large amount of computing power. The trained models are then deployed in the final computing environment to execute inferences as actual events occur. During runtime, model inferences must be performed once the events produced in the near past have been gathered, but before the actual situation the models try to predict occurs. This sets timing restrictions on the inference executions, turning the problem into a real-time problem.

In incident management processes, for example, the lower layers detect failures by examining the event streams received from sensors through (wireless) networks and gateways, which aggregate this information and send it to a control center, where ML incident identification models are enacted following the sensors-to-cloud model.

However, as the size of MGs grows, it is necessary to distribute the execution of the inferences of predictive monitoring models to meet the real-time requirements and for scalability concerns, moving this execution as close as possible to the sources of events, as predicting at the lowest level of operation keeps the response time as short as possible. With many sensors, the capacity of these devices can become a bottleneck. In particular, during emergencies, the number of events increases substantially, highlighting the need for offloading calculations.

We propose a distributed architecture for events inference using predictive monitoring models distributed across nodes in the hierarchical infrastructure, collecting events generated from the devices and sending them as a stream from the edge gateways to the substations in the fog and to the control center in the cloud. Nodes are provisioned with the offline-trained predictive models required for their predictions, moving the computation closest to where the data are being generated. To ensure that prediction times are met even with load and data imbalances, the nodes use admission control strategies to determine if there are sufficient resources to process an event; otherwise, the architecture offloads events and inference processing over a hierarchical structure based on the edge/fog/cloud continuum.

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II. THE PREDICTIVE MONITORING MODELS

To support predictive monitoring, we rely on online event predictions based on a time-window [4,7,8,9]. This is a supervised learning strategy that starts with a time-labelled events dataset that is used to train the prediction models. These are then used for inference execution (model execution) of actual, online observed events. While our focus is on inference execution, we provide some insight into the model training.

The training dataset is a time-labeled series of events observed in the system (the MG), their type, and the location or device where they have been produced. Events appear in a sequence ordered by the time of appearance. A sliding window created input-output pairs to train the model. The input is the observation window, that is, the time span in which the system events are observed to infer the prediction. The output is the prediction window, that is, the time span in which the event prediction is defined. There is a guard time between the end of the observation window and the start of the prediction window, which is considered as a parameter in the model training.

The observation window (whose time span is defined beforehand) slides over the dataset, and at each significant position, events within the window are selected as inputs, whereas the corresponding future observation, each event in the so-called prediction window (whose length is also predefined and starts after the end of the observation window plus the guard time) becomes the output. This process is repeated for each position in the dataset, generating a set of training pairs (events in the observation window and an outgoing event). These relationships represent a causal relationship between the events in the observation window and the outgoing event. With the input-output pairs created,

several ML models can be trained (a survey of which can be found in [10]).

Taking only the events produced in a single device as the training dataset, we can obtain the models to perform predictions at that node. If the training dataset contains all the events produced by the devices connected to the same microgrid controller we obtain the models at the controller node (some of which will reflect interactions between devices in the controller domain), and as we ascend in the hierarchy, we obtain larger datasets for which wider models are obtained. The quality of the predictions is highly dependent on the quality of the dataset, the values of the observation and prediction window lengths, and the technique chosen to create the prediction models.

After the training phase, we obtain a set of models that produce a prediction about an event type in the prediction window for events occurring in the observation window. If all models are set in a unique location, all events must be moved there to obtain predictions, as is done today in the edge-cloud model [10]. Training models as close as possible to the sources of events is an active area of research [11, 12], but current practice still requires a large processing power for the training phase; therefore, this is performed in environments with plenty of resources [13].

Figure 1 shows a sketch of the inference process for each processing node. The observation windows, time guard and prediction windows are observed. When an event arrives at a node, it must update the already open observation windows, and its own observation window is also open. At the end of the observation time, inferences are made by applying each of the available models to the window, some of which generate events predictions that are valid for the timespan of its prediction window.

Interestingly enough, any kind of model can be enacted

Fig 1: Inference process

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provided it takes the observation window as input and produces a prediction window with the event type, the execution environment is properly set, and the models processing time does not exceed the guard time, which probably occurs if many observation windows are open at the same time, forcing the execution of the models just at the end of the observation window.

If this condition is not met, then the incoming event should not be accepted for opening its observation window, and this must be performed elsewhere. Among the several techniques that have been proposed for the cooperation between devices with limited resources, offloading [10] offers a trade-off between energy, accuracy, and latency for different models. Our proposal is to offload the event upwards in the hierarchy, to the closest node, in a recursive manner up to the uppermost node, in the cloud.

III. THE PREDICTIVE MONITORING ARCHITECTURE

Our proposed predictive monitoring architecture follows a distributed architecture with layers (bottom-up, see Figure 3):

- sensors connected to gateways by wireless networks; they measure the state of (physical) elements in the MG, taking the physical magnitude they handle and setting thresholds in order to generate events of different types, which are then moved to gateways by means of the appropriate protocols (e.g. MQTT).
- gateways (edge) are limited devices whose main responsibility is to ingest the events, build upward event streams implemented by queues on message-oriented middleware, and connect these events to the edge.
- microgrid controllers nodes (edge), each one is fed with the event streams coming from its gateway; they run their models and send the predictions upwards.
- substation nodes (fog) for cooperation between the microgrid controllers located in the same regional area, performing the same operation as the events received at their input event streams.
- the headquarters center node (cloud) is the top data center or private cloud, with sufficient resources to run all possible models, if required.

The predictive monitoring nodes (edge, fog, cloud) are fed with event streams; therefore, on each event arrival, the node opens an observation window and updates the others as required. Whenever an observation window closes, the models held by the node are applied to the window, and an inference is made, possibly rendering an event prediction. Event predictions can be used at any node to launch control operations or sent to the control center for visualization and registration.

Events are only produced at the sensors and move upwards in the hierarchy, traversing all nodes to the top control center. At each level, the events feed different prediction models, as previously explained. Each event is fed to predict a local model first, then potentially one step up a regional model, and finally, a top model affecting a wider geographical area. This is a purely hierarchical model; therefore, no direct cooperation

between siblings will be considered, as this may break the locality conditions and the hierarchical nature of information flow (it is likely that siblings will also have an excess workload in the event of a burst arrival).

To meet real-time requirements in producing predictions, an additional upwards stream must be provided between layers, so that events that a node cannot process due to limited availability of resources will be offloaded to the next upper node with available resources. Our key assumption is that on-site prediction (closest to the event source) can be offloaded to the upper layer, incurring small additional costs; in extreme cases, even a complete layer can be skipped. We propose applying a mechanism based on admission control to decide whether to process an incoming event at this level or to offload it to the upper level.

Fig. 2. Model of the processing node.

The Prediction Module (Fig. 2, center) is the main functional component of the processing node. It holds the prediction models and the engine. In its simplest configuration, it contains: a Windows Manager, in charge of opening new observation windows and updating already active as events arrive; the Memory Manager that accounts for the available memory in order to check if a new observation window can be held; the Model Manager, which contains the predictive models charged in memory (and supports model deployment or updating operations); and the Inference Manager that schedules the launching of inferences -model execution- at the end of the observation window time, records the time elapsed in the execution of models, and submits the resulting predictions (event prediction vertical arrow).

The Prediction Module performs the inference process shown in Figure 1. The Model Manager must contain the models pertaining to its region of interest -those that predict the appearance of events in any of the devices in its region. To implement the offloading strategy, the models that should be executed by any of their dependent nodes must also be in the memory of this processing node. In general, models will take

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as input the events observed in any observation window as input and will produce, as a result, a set of predicted events that will probably appear during the prediction window. Occasionally, as in the 13th and 14th observation windows in Figure 1, no events are predicted (the upwards prediction message can be skipped). In fact, prediction windows do not require memory once the outgoing messages containing the event predictions and their lifetimes are sent. In Figure 1, we depict the simplest mechanism in which all models are applied to all observation windows. The reason for keeping both types of entering events apart is that the models must handle each of them -regular ones in the inward stream and offloaded in the offloading input stream.

There are two Admission Controls (AC): one for the regular incoming events in the inwards stream, and the other for the events in the offloading input stream. The regular AC sends a copy of the event to the upward stream directly to reduce latency in the upper layers. This is not necessary for the offloading AC. Each one must ensure that there are sufficient resources to create a new observation window (in the pictures, we have set windows of the same size; this is not strictly necessary, only to know the size of the memory required by the observation window beforehand). A memory check was performed by the Memory Manager. In addition, it must be guaranteed that there is sufficient processor time to perform the inferences (execute models) over that new observation window, once it finishes and before the time guard is complete. In the example shown in Figure 1, the observation windows that start at $t=0$ for $e_1, e_2, e_3, e_4, e_5,$ and e_6 must be processed before the time guard (dark box in the figure). That is, for the time at which each observation window closes, the maximum number of windows that can be processed is the guard time divided by the average model execution time. The Inference Manager provides the number of model executions (observation windows) scheduled to execute at the same time as the incoming event; if it cannot guarantee that this last window will be processed within its time guard, the event is rejected to open its observation window.

For scarce resource devices or if a high rate of events arrival is expected, it is advisable to calculate the maximum number of observation windows and maximum number of model inferences that can be made in each time unit and set these values as configuration static values. A more dynamic behavior can be obtained if measures of the available memory and processor capacity are taken in real time; therefore, the maximum values could fluctuate depending on small variations in memory occupation or inference times.

Regular streaming handles events and moves them up in the hierarchy (Fig. 2, right). It is composed by:

- Inwards Stream: Input events generated by the lower level are placed in this queue. The underlying messaging platform must support the connection of several publishers to this endpoint, where an MQTT subscriber consumes the incoming events.
- Upwards Stream: The events that arrive at the processing node are copied and sent upwards by means of this stream that is accessed by the MQTT producer. This output stream is connected to the inward stream at the upper level, where aggregation occurs because it receives

events from several upwards streams at the same level. This connection uses the network and thus incurs transmission delays.

- Regular N-level Admission Control. The events that are admitted for processing enter the Prediction Module; otherwise, they are sent to the Offloading upward stream to be processed at the upper level as offloaded events.

If there are no offloading mechanisms and no resources are available, the event should be enqueued to wait for resources, thus delaying the production of predictions. As this effect would be particularly dangerous at the lowest levels, which have scarce resources, we added offloading streams to gather the events discarded by the AC at the N-1 level. The AC also checks the health of the node itself; therefore, if the prediction part is down, it redirects all events to the next upper layer, turning all incoming events into offloaded events.

The offloading streams (Fig. 1, left) handle events that cannot be processed at the lower nodes.

- The Offloading Input Stream is the input-events queue for offloaded events. This is not available for the lowermost nodes. As explained, events arriving through it, aggregated from the offloading upward streams at the downward level, can be either processed at this level (rendering the offloaded work as solved) or sent upwards.
- Offloading Upwards Stream: All the events coming from the offloading input streams in lower levels that have not been solved are aggregated here, as are the events from downwards levels that could not be processed there.
- Offloaded Admission Control receives events offloaded from the lower levels in the hierarchy and accepts them for processing or resending to the Offloading upward stream. Note that in this case, the event is not duplicated to be sent upwards; it is either processed at this level, or it will go upwards until the highest node is reached.

III. VALIDATION

Figure 3 shows an example of the application scenario of the model. The lowest-level processors do not have incoming offloading streams; however, because they have scarce resources, they may feed offloading events into substation nodes. These, in turn, are both able to handle offloaded events and produce offloaded events if they cannot make predictions for some events. The top node of the Control Center is assumed to be able to process all regular and offloaded events; however, if no resources are available on the arrival of an event, the input streams will behave as queues, storing these incoming events until resources are available.

While processing closest to the source allows lower response times, it also implies more workload on the nodes with scarce resources; on the other hand, moving upper in the hierarchy brings more resources, at the cost of traversing the network and higher latency. Let us review the life cycle of events to understand the run-time performance of the architecture using the application scenario shown in Figure 3. We assume that all events gathered in a Gateway will open its own observation window and launch the execution of prediction models in each of the processors that control the zone; this is, Gateway 1.1.2

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events will be processed by MGController 1.1.2, Substation 1.1 and ControlCenter 1.

Events are generated by sensors; they encode the type of event, sensor id, value of time, and other data. Sensors send these events to their controlling gateway; network technology can be wired or wireless, incurring a negligible network delay. In Figure 3, we show an event received by Gateway1.2.2 (the bold lines on the right side) and a second event in Gateway1.1.2 (the bold lines on the left side).

The event is received in the inward stream of the edge processor; the design of the admission control strives for no-delay submission of the event upwards. In addition, if resources are available, a job is performed to generate a prediction. The same occurs upward in the remaining nodes. This path is followed by the event in Gateway1.2.2, taken by MGController1.2.2, by Substation1.2, and by ControlCenter1, in which there are available resources; therefore, the prediction models are applied, which eventually produce predictions. The prediction time for an incoming event is its observation window timespan plus the guard time (plus network delays, deemed negligible).

The event generated at Gateway1.1.2 is not lucky. It finds MGController1.1.2 busy processing other events, so first it is sent upwards so Substation1.1 can take its duties; then it is rejected by the admission control, and therefore a copy is sent through the offloading upwards stream to Substation1.1 offloading input stream. Again, no luck, Substation1.1 is full. Then, both the regular and offloading admission controls reject it, so the event is also sent to the Offloading input stream of ControlCenter1. This holds plenty of resources and is able to process the event with MGController1.1.2,

Substation1.1, and ControlCenter1 models. The time to predict an event that comes through an offloading stream is roughly the number of network links it traverses to reach any available processor upwards, plus the processing time at that processor, plus the time spent in the admission controls.

In these operations, we can assume that computational resources are more constraining than memory. The computational cost of creating and updating an observation window is constant, as is the cost of executing models; however, the costs of executing models are far higher than those of the others.

We characterize node resources as the number of jobs (window model executions) that they may perform in the considered time unit. For homogeneous computing infrastructures, the node computation resources and job-processing costs are similar. However, this is not the case for an edge-cloud computing scenario. Cloud nodes are substantially more powerful, whereas running on the edge has the opposite effect. The number of available resources that a node holds implies capacity restrictions. Figure 3 shows the nodes with different numbers of jobs that they can perform simultaneously.

Doing an actual deployment is not possible before evaluating risks; therefore, we evaluated the scenario shown in Figure 3 by means of simulation (code available at <https://github.com/jandion/predictiveDCI>). We assumed that all nodes contain models to process events of any type generated by the devices in their zone or region; each node contains the models corresponding to its children nodes for offloading processing; memory for models and observation windows are supposed to be available and are not considered;

Fig. 3. Example of application scenario with hierarchical structure.

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and no communication time will be considered. Parameters are:

- time guard: 1 second
- observation window time span: 300 seconds
- prediction window time span: 180 seconds
- MGcontrollers capacity 10 jobs/second, 100 milliseconds models processing time
- Substations capacity 20 jobs/second, 50 milliseconds model processing time
- ControlCenter capacity 200 jobs/second, 5 milliseconds model processing time.

Fig. 4. Regular (bottom) and offloaded (top) jobs per node, low event rate.

The architecture was evaluated under different loading conditions (Fig 4-6). Each figure shows the number of events (jobs) processed per second in each processor. The bottom part shows the number of events in the regular inwards stream of each processor and the upper part shows the number of events processed from the offloading input stream of each processor.

Fig. 5. Regular (bottom) and offloaded (top) jobs per node, medium event rate.

In the first evaluation scenario (Fig. 4), events were generated by each sensor following an exponential distribution for the time between arrivals with $\lambda=0.05$, which can be considered as a low rate of events. As expected, MGControllers 1.1.1, 1.1.2, 1.2.1 and 1.2.2 can cope with most or all incoming events. We are supposing each event also will be handled by at least a model in each of the processors it traverses, from lowest to

uppermost, Substation 1.1 number of events is approximately the sum of events coming from MGControllers 1.1.1 and 1.1.2. The same occurs for Substation 1.2 with its children, and again for CC 1 with respect to 1.1 and 1.2. The regular part of the processors seems to be able to cope with incoming events, so no event is sent to the offloading streams or sporadically.

The second evaluation scenario sets the distribution of the generation of events with $\lambda=0.1$, which is quite close to the processing threshold. In this case, some events traversed the offloading path upwards, as indicated by the number of offloading events (Figure 5, top). The lowest-level processors operate under saturated conditions, forcing them to offload events to their upper processors. In the first scenario, events were seldom offloaded, and now this occurred often. This corresponds to transient situations; therefore, some offloaded events may still occur at the intermediate nodes.

Finally, when the event generation rate reaches values above the processing threshold, the edge and fog nodes are usually offloaded, requiring the Control Center node to solve the emergency situation, for example, with $\lambda=0.2$. When the uppermost node capacities are surpassed, the entry streams behave as queues, so events must wait there to be served (Figure 6).

Fig. 6. Regular (bottom) and offloaded (top) jobs per node, high event rate.

We performed some experiments on inference execution using Random Forests (50 trees) on a dataset of events containing 108 different types of events and valid models, on an Intel i7-3720QM 2.6GHz, 8 virtual cores with a HyperThreading computer, 16GB RAM running Ubuntu x64 15.10. We set 1 s as the minimal time step, a 300 s observation window, a 1 s time guard and a 300 s prediction window. We ran 108 inferences/predictions per second, using 4.4 MB per model and memory occupation for an observation window of approximately 300 bytes. The stress tests suggested that up to 300 inferences could be made per second.

The results of both the simulations and inference experiments suggest that the architecture proposed with all its elements will be able to submit the events to the nodes in which the models are actually deployed, and can also check for the availability of resources in the current node to accept the event processing or offload it to its next upper layer node, thus ensuring that the predictive models will be run on all events.

V. CONCLUSIONS

We demonstrated a distributed architecture for the inference execution of predictive monitoring models that supports offloading capabilities. The hierarchical nature of DCIs control applications, such as smart grids, nicely supports the offloading capabilities by means of queues supporting the event streams in a vertical-upwards sense. This architecture is model-agnostic, provided that the specific machine learning model operates on event windows. Our architecture ensures that the models allocated to each node will get their inferences executed, thus producing predictions only if the node receives sufficient resources to perform the inference; otherwise, the incoming events will be sent to the upper layer by the offloading queue for execution.

Our future plans are to leverage the architecture by considering security and safety requirements, its application to other types of predictive models, designing the support for run-time dynamic on-the-fly deployment of models to available nodes, and setting the ground for automatic generation of control operations that would lead to autonomic management of DCIs.

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